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The Role of Sustainable Financial Practices in Shaping Corporate Risk

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Abstract: *This study investigates the impact of sustainable financial practices, expressed through ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) performance, on corporate bankruptcy risk, using the Altman Z-score as a predictive indicator. The research aims to determine whether the integration of sustainability criteria contributes to strengthening firms' financial resilience. A balanced panel of 20 multinational companies, covering diverse sectors (technology, energy, automotive, consumer goods, retail) and the 2020–2024 period, was analysed. Variables included ESG component scores, profitability ratios (ROA, ROE), and leverage, with data processed through econometric panel regression with fixed effects. Results indicate that profitability, particularly ROA, is the strongest determinant of lower bankruptcy risk, while excessive reliance on equity returns (ROE) may increase vulnerability. Governance exhibits a marginal but positive role in mitigating risk, whereas environmental and social dimensions show no significant short-term effects, possibly due to implementation costs and delayed benefits. Leverage, contrary to theoretical expectations, was not statistically relevant in the model. Sectoral analysis revealed strong performance and stability in Technology & IT, contrasted by volatility and weaker ESG integration in Retail & Luxury. The findings highlight the importance of combining traditional financial indicators with ESG metrics for comprehensive risk assessment. From a practical perspective, integrating sustainability – especially governance – into corporate strategy can enhance resilience, inform investment decisions, and support long-term financial stability.*

Keywords: *ESG performance; Bankruptcy risk; Altman Z-score; Financial resilience; Panel regression.*

1. Introduction

In recent decades, the concept of sustainable finance has become increasingly important in the corporate and investment environment (Oprean-Stan, 2025). Investors and regulators are putting significant pressure on companies to adopt environmentally, socially, and governance (ESG) responsible business practices. For example, assets managed globally according to ESG criteria reached approximately \$35.3 trillion in 2020, representing approximately 36% of total assets under management (Global Sustainable Investment Alliance, 2021). This development highlights the increasingly high expectations of stakeholders that companies integrate sustainable financial practices into their business strategy.

In this context, the question arises as to what extent a company's ESG performance is reflected in its financial stability and risk of bankruptcy. The purpose of ESG assessment is essentially to assess a company's ability to operate in a responsible and sustainable manner in the long term, while avoiding critical bankruptcy situations. Numerous financial scandals and corporate crises in recent decades (accounting fraud, serious violations of environmental regulations, or poor governance practices) have demonstrated that ignorance of ESG issues can lead to massive losses and even the collapse of companies. Thus, understanding the link between sustainable practices and risk at the firm level, in particular the risk of insolvency or bankruptcy, has become a topical concern and a major focus for corporate management, creditors, and investors (Thiele, 2024).

The literature also suggests that a better ESG profile is often associated with high financial performance or at least no negative impact (Friede et al., 2015), indicating that sustainable commitment does not conflict with economic objectives but, on the contrary, can support the long-term stability of the company. More empirical studies indicate that companies with high ESG scores tend to have a lower risk profile compared to those with poor sustainable performance. For example, an analysis of the US market showed that companies with high levels of corporate social responsibility have significantly lower financial risks, as these companies enjoy greater credibility with creditors and a lower frequency of default (Boubaker et al., 2020). Cooper and Uzun (2019) reported similar findings, highlighting that the probability of bankruptcy is lower for companies with superior sustainability performance. Similarly, a study of the emerging market in Brazil showed that firms that adopt sound practices across the three ESG dimensions are less likely to become insolvent, suggesting that sustainability contributes to mitigating operational risk (Santos & Junior, 2024). These results support the thesis of a protective effect of sustainable financial practices on the stability and sustainability of firms.

However, the literature is not unanimous, with different perspectives or essential conditions also existing. Some recent research highlights that the ESG-financial risk relationship may depend on the economic context and time horizon. Habermann and Fischer (2023), analysing US companies during periods of economic expansion (2010- 2019), found that a high level of sustainability performance does not significantly reduce the probability of bankruptcy in favourable economic conditions. Moreover, these authors show that a sharp increase in a firm's ESG score during such prosperous periods may even lead to an increase in the risk of bankruptcy in the short term, as the benefits of better stakeholder relations do not have time to materialize immediately, while the costs of implementing sustainable practices may affect current performance. In their interpretation, investments in sustainability act as a kind of "insurance" mechanism that proves its full usefulness especially in times of crisis by contributing to the resilience of the firm, even if in times of economic boom, the positive effects on risk are not immediate. Such findings do not necessarily contradict the long-term benefits of ESG practices, but they highlight the need for a nuanced analysis of the link between ESG and risk, considering contextual factors.

Given the considerable theoretical and practical interest of the subject, this paper aims to investigate the impact of sustainable financial practices on risk at the firm level, focusing on the relationship between ESG scores and the risk of bankruptcy of companies. The originality of the approach lies in its integrated approach to these concepts: correlating segmented sustainability scores (environmental, social, governance) with a traditional bankruptcy prediction indicator – the Altman Z-score – and other relevant financial indicators, such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and leverage (financial leverage). In the existing literature, few studies have directly examined the link between ESG scores and Altman's Z score, with most risk analyses focusing either on market indicators (stock volatility, cost of capital) or credit ratings. Therefore, this research makes an original contribution by exploring this relationship in a quantitative framework, using current data and controlling for the influence of classic financial variables on bankruptcy risk. The main objective of this paper is to assess whether and to what extent firms' ESG performance influences bankruptcy risk, as measured by the Altman Z-score. In line with the direction of most previous studies, the basic hypothesis is that firms with higher ESG scores have a lower risk of bankruptcy, demonstrating that sustainable financial practices positively influence the financial stability of the firm. This hypothesis will be tested on a relevant sample of companies, using statistical analysis to determine the existence and direction of the relationship between the variables in question.

In terms of structure, the paper is organized into five sections. The first section introduces the topic, the second section outlines the theoretical framework of the research, focusing on the literature on ESG, financial performance, and bankruptcy risk, including key models (ROA, ROE, financial leverage, and the Altman Z-score model). The third section describes the research methodology, including the sample characteristics and the econometric model proposed for testing the hypothesis. The fourth section presents the empirical analysis and the results obtained, highlighting the relationship identified between ESG scores and bankruptcy risk. The final sections bring together the main conclusions of the study, highlighting the contributions of the paper to the enrichment of specialist knowledge, the improvement of managerial practices, as well as the limitations of the research and future research directions.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1. The ESG Concept and its Relevance in the Context of Bankruptcy Risk

The concept of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) defines corporate sustainability criteria across three major dimensions: environmental protection, social responsibility, and corporate governance quality. These dimensions provide a holistic framework for assessing a company's practices beyond financial indicators, reflecting how the firm manages issues such as its environmental impact, its relationship with employees, customers, and the community, as well as the transparency, ethics, and efficiency of decision-making processes at the management level (Malik et al., 2025; Portney, 2015). ESG scores, developed by specialized agencies (LSEG Workgroup, MSCI, S&P Global, Refinitiv, Sustainalytics, etc.) summarize a company's performance on these components, allowing for comparability between companies. The integration of ESG criteria into financial analysis has expanded significantly in recent years, fuelled by increasingly stringent non-financial reporting requirements and international initiatives such as the UN Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI). As a result, investors are paying more attention to ESG scores, considering them benchmarks of companies' long-term risk profiles. The literature highlights that robust performance on ESG dimensions is often associated with financial stability and a reduced probability of extreme adverse outcomes for the firm (Erokhin et al., 2020; Rusu & Oprean-Stan, 2024a, 2024b). A notable example is the meta-analysis conducted by Friede et al. (2015) which aggregated the conclusions of over 2,000 empirical studies and found that the vast majority of them report a positive or neutral link between corporate sustainability practices and financial performance, suggesting that ESG commitment does not negatively affect, but may even support, a company's financial performance. Therefore, there is a clear economic motivation for integrating sustainable practices: they can help build a solid reputation, improve stakeholder relations, and reduce exposure to environmental, social, or regulatory risks.

2.2. The Altman Z-score Model and Traditional Financial Indicators

To avoid the risk of a company going bankrupt, corporate finance has developed several overall indicators over time, the most established being the Altman Z-score. The Z-score model introduced by Altman in 1968, combines five essential financial indicators relating to liquidity, profitability, solvency, indebtedness, and asset efficiency into a single score that estimates the probability of a company going bankrupt within a period of approximately two years. A high Z-score indicates a solid financial position, i.e., a low risk of insolvency, while a low Z-score signals financial vulnerability and a high risk of bankruptcy. The model was subsequently adjusted for different types of companies and tested in various markets, largely maintaining its predictive accuracy. Even today, the Altman Z-score remains a benchmark tool for assessing the insolvency risk of firms (Altman et al., 2017; Maulana, 2024; Say, 2024).

In addition to the Z-score, bankruptcy risk assessment is also based on simple financial indicators such as profitability and leverage. ROA (Return on Assets) is the profitability of total assets and measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate profit, being the ratio between net profit and total assets (Masditok et al., 2024). ROE (Return on Equity) represents the return on equity and shows the return that shareholders obtain from the capital they have invested. In principle, high ROA and ROE values indicate robust financial performance and the company's ability to generate sufficient internal resources, which is associated with a lower risk of bankruptcy (Berk & DeMarzo, 2020). Financial leverage expresses the degree of indebtedness of a company, for example the ratio of debt to assets, and is directly related to risk. High leverage implies high financial obligations (interest, instalments), amplifying the firm's vulnerability to shocks, while low leverage indicates a more solid capital structure and a lower risk of insolvency. Therefore, it is essential that the analysis of the relationship between ESG and bankruptcy risk also controls for these traditional financial factors, whose influence on the probability of bankruptcy is well known (Fridson & Alvarez, 2022).

2.3. Mechanisms of ESG Performance Influence on Firm Risk

In short, ESG practices can act as a corporate risk mitigation tool: improved stakeholder relations, enhanced reputation, and rigorous governance reduce the likelihood of major adverse events such as litigation, fines, and various scandals that threaten the company's viability. At the same time, companies

with high ESG performance often benefit from lower financing costs and increased access to capital, as investors and lenders perceive them as safer and more transparent entities. Empirical studies confirm these mechanisms, for example, transparency in social responsibility practices is associated with lower cost of equity (Cheng et al., 2014), and high ESG scores correlate with better credit ratings and lower risk premiums (Tan & Tsionas, 2022).

On the other hand, the traditional perspective (Dunn & Burton, 2006) argues that resources directed toward environmental or social objectives may represent costs that diminish profits and may even increase risk if the firm wastes capital on unproductive initiatives. In this view, only sustainable investments that bring concrete economic benefits can be justified, so ESG practices could negatively affect the company's financial performance and stability over time.

2.4. The State of Empirical Research on ESG and Bankruptcy Risk

Numerous empirical studies have investigated the link between ESG indicators and the probability of bankruptcy, with most finding an inverse relationship between the two. For example, Boubaker et al. (2020) show, based on US data, that firms with high corporate responsibility scores face a significantly lower risk of financial distress than those with low involvement in such practices. Other analyses confirm these results, with companies with superior ESG performance having lower probabilities of insolvency (Chen et al., 2020; Cooper & Uzun, 2019). In a recent study, Antunes et al. (2023) found, using a dynamic efficiency analysis methodology, that firms with high ESG scores have a lower incidence of financial distress, an effect attributed to robust corporate governance that reduces the risk of insolvency. Habermann and Fischer (2023) did not identify a significant effect of ESG scores on the probability of bankruptcy during favourable economic periods and observed that a sharp increase in sustainability efforts in such contexts may slightly increase short-term financial risk, suggesting that ESG benefits are particularly pronounced in times of economic stress, rather than necessarily during boom periods.

Another aspect investigated in the literature is the possible endogenous nature of the relationship between ESG and risk: is it ESG performance that leads to risk reduction, or are low-risk firms with good financial performance simply better able to finance sustainable initiatives? Many studies attempt to resolve this causality issue using appropriate methodologies, such as instrumental variables or matched sample models. Boubaker et al. (2020) rigorously controlled for potential reverse causality effects and confirmed that the relationship between corporate responsibility practices and bankruptcy risk remains negative and significant even after such adjustments, strengthening the argument for a real effect of sustainable practices on risk reduction. However, the topic remains open to debate, and further research is needed to more clearly identify the causal mechanisms and possible variations across economic sectors or geographical regions.

In Romania, at the national level, literature dedicated to ESG is still in its infancy, but there are some contributions that indicate similar trends. Nitescu and Cristea (2020) analyse the Romanian banking sector and highlight the importance of integrating ESG risks into commercial banks' strategies. They find that banks with high profitability (ROA) and high debt ratios were less willing to implement ESG risk management strategies, a sign that institutions in a very good financial situation feel less pressure to change. These results highlight the need for proactive adoption of sustainable practices even by companies with favourable financial indicators, as well as the role of open governance towards sustainability in accelerating these initiatives (Zaharia, 2024).

2.5. Gaps in Existing Literature and Directions for Current Research

Despite the progress made in the literature, several notable gaps remain. First, most studies have focused on developed economies and large, listed companies, which raises questions about the applicability of the findings to emerging markets or smaller firms. Second, many traditional financial factors, such as ROA, ROE, or leverage, are not always correlated in existing analyses, which may distort the estimation of the real impact of ESG on risk. In addition, the heterogeneous results reported across economic periods or sectors suggest a need to investigate the specific conditions under which the link between ESG and bankruptcy risk is strongest. Finally, almost no study has directly combined ESG scores as an established bankruptcy prediction model, such as the Z-score. Although this research focuses on large

companies listed on indices such as EURO STOXX 50 and S&P 500, it is essential that future studies extend the analysis to medium and small-sized enterprises, as well as to emerging markets, to verify whether the relationship identified between ESG scores and bankruptcy risk remains robust in different economic and financial contexts. This paper also aims to address these gaps by examining the relationship between ESG scores and bankruptcy risk in an integrated model that includes the financial indicators mentioned above, to determine the extent to which sustainable practices provide added value in risk anticipation compared to traditional financial indicators.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Objective

The main objective of this research is to assess the influence of corporate sustainability practices, as expressed by ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) scores, and financial performance on the bankruptcy risk of companies, as measured by the Z_{ALTMAN} indicator. The study aims to determine whether the integration of ESG criteria and solid financial parameters contributes to reducing financial and operational risks, thereby strengthening organizational resilience.

3.2. Data Sample and Variables

The sample consists of a balanced set of 20 large international companies operating in various sectors, including consumer goods, technology, energy, automotive, and creative industries. Among the companies included are Danone S.A., Iberdrola S.A., Kering S.A., Siemens AG, Adidas AG, Tesla Inc., Microsoft Corp., Apple Inc., General Motors, and Starbucks Corporation, covering both European economies (companies listed in the EURO SOTXX 50) and American economies (companies in the S&P 500). These companies were selected based on the availability of data for ESG and financial variables during the period analysed and their relevance to corporate sustainability.

Data is collected for the period 2020–2024, representing a balanced panel of 5 years and 20 entities, providing 100 observations. Data sources include public financial databases (Yahoo Finance) and ESG aggregators – LSEG Workspace ESG scores, which provide standardized scores for the E, S, and G components. All financial data (ROA, ROE, LEV) are expressed in annual consolidated values at the company level.

The dependent variable is Z_{ALTMAN} – the Altman Z-score, which measures a firm's risk of bankruptcy based on balance sheet and income statement indicators. The explanatory variables are divided into two categories: (1) ESG indicators: E – environmental score; S – social score; G – governance score; (2) Financial indicators: LEV – leverage (degree of indebtedness); ROA – return on assets; ROE – return on equity.

The model used to determine the Altman Z score is presented in Equation 1.

$$Z = 1.2X_1 + 1.4X_2 + 3.3X_3 + 0.6X_4 + 1.0X_5 \quad (1)$$

The variables were calculated as presented in Equations 2-6.

$$X_1 = \frac{\text{Working capital}}{\text{Total Assets}} \quad (2)$$

$$X_2 = \frac{\text{Retained Earnings}}{\text{Total Assets}} \quad (3)$$

$$X_3 = \frac{\text{EBIT}}{\text{Total Assets}} \quad (4)$$

$$X_4 = \frac{\text{Market Value of Equity}}{\text{Total Liabilities}} \quad (5)$$

$$X_5 = \frac{\text{Total Revenue}}{\text{Total Assets}} \quad (6)$$

According to the Altman risk assessment model (Z-Score), the financial interpretation is as follows:

- $Z > 2.99$ – safe zone: stable company with minimal risk of insolvency.
- $1.8 < Z \leq 2.99$ – grey zone: moderate risk, the company must be closely monitored.

- $Z < 1.8$ – danger zone: high risk of bankruptcy (CFI, n.d.).

To make a consistent comparison between companies in different sectors, we have grouped the 20 companies analysed into five distinct categories, namely:

- Essential consumer goods: Danone S.A., Procter & Gamble, L'Oréal, Coca-Cola;
- Retail and Luxury: Adidas, Kering S.A., Floor&Decor Holdings Inc., Starbucks Corporation;
- Automotive and Aeronautics: Tesla, General Motors, Airbus SE, Siemens AG;
- Technology and IT: SAP SE, Microsoft, Apple, ASML Holding;
- Energy, Utilities, and Telecommunications: ExxonMobil, Iberdrola S.A., Deutsche Telekom, Cisco Systems Inc.

After grouping, for each indicator, including the Altman Z score, ESG components, return on equity, and financial leverage, the average annual values for the 2020-2024 period were calculated at the sector level using the Average function in Excel for a comparative analysis of their evolution.

3.3. Regression Model

To assess the influence of ESG and financial variables on bankruptcy risk, the following panel regression model was formulated, with fixed cross-sectional effects to control for heterogeneity between firms (Equation 7):

$$Z_{ALT_{it}} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 E_{it} + \beta_2 S_{it} + \beta_3 G_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + \beta_5 ROA_{it} + \beta_6 ROE_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (7)$$

The model is estimated using the Panel Least Squares method, with fixed effects, based on a balanced panel.

4. Results

4.1. Analysis of the Dynamics of the Indicators

The analysis of the evolution of financial indicators for companies grouped by sector of activity highlights the trends specific to each field, pointing out both sectors with accelerated growth and those with potential for improvement.

Table 1. Average E, S, and G scores by sector (2020-2024)

Sector	E score	S	G Score
Auto & Aeronautics	82.7	80.25	67.9
Essential consumer goods	73.8	79.1	71.95
Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications	79	87.6	70.1
Retail & Luxury	70.55	74.6	63.15
Technology & IT	71.6	86.1	87.3

Source: own calculations, using Excel

Based on ESG averages from 2020–2024 (presented in Table 1), Auto & Aeronautics is the leader in the environmental component (82.7) thanks to investments in efficiency and clean technologies, but its governance (67.9) lags significantly behind, requiring a strategy to strengthen internal controls and transparency. The Essential Consumer Goods industry scores similarly across all three pillars (E=73.8) (S=79.1) and (G=71.95), signalling a stable profile but without excellence, so it would be worth focusing on sustainable innovation and strengthening anti-corruption policies to rise above the usual level. Similarly, Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications excel socially (87.6) through good health and inclusion practices, but governance (70.1) remains below potential, suggesting a need for independent audits and more robust anti-fraud policies. Retail & Luxury lags on all dimensions (E=70.6), (S=74.6) and (G=63.15), reflecting poorly implemented working standards. This is the sector that requires immediate intervention with structural reforms and close monitoring. The Technology & IT industry performs best in social and governance (86.1 and 87.3, respectively) but remains close to the average in the environment dimension (E=71.6), indicating untapped potential for reducing its carbon footprint

and adopting renewable energy. Overall, priority should be given to the entire Retail & Luxury sector, governance in the Automotive and Aeronautics industries, and improving the environmental factor in IT, to remedy the progress of these sectors.

Table 2. Average return on assets – ROA

Year	Auto & Aeronautics	Essential consumer goods	Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications	Retail & Luxury	Technology & IT
2020	1.56	8.08	2.51	5.30	13.83
2021	5.58	9.34	5.59	10.74	18.98
2022	6.82	9.30	8.45	8.11	17.32
2023	7.05	9.45	7.93	6.84	18.86
2024	4.65	9.77	6.16	5.81	16.67

Source: own calculations, using Excel

Regarding ROA (presented in Table 2), the Technology & IT and Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications sectors peaked in 2021–22 (18.98% and 8.45%) and fell to 16.67% and 6.16% respectively by 2024, highlighting volatility. The Auto & Aeronautics group rose from 1.56% in 2020 to 7.05% in 2023 and fell to 4.65%, recording the highest cumulative growth. The Essential consumer goods sector remained stable between 8.08% and 9.77%, with a slight upward trend. Similarly, the Retail & Luxury sector lost almost half of its ROA after peaking at 10.74% in 2021, recording the sharpest decline.

Table 3. Average return on equity - ROE

Year	Auto & Aeronautics	Essential consumer goods	Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications	Retail & Luxury	Technology & IT
2020	2.62	23.02	10.17	9.95	39.43
2021	27.02	26.46	15.44	4.42	64.72
2022	23.36	25.01	22.00	4.51	71.94
2023	21.08	25.32	23.28	-4.70	73.98
2024	15.69	26.23	18.04	-3.06	62

Source: own calculations, using Excel

Regarding ROE (see Table 3), The Technology & IT and Auto & Aeronautics sectors exploded in 2021 (64.7% vs. 27.0%), continued to rise until 2023 for IT (73.98%), then declined until 2024 (62.26% and 15.69%), marking high volatility. The Essential Consumer Goods industry remained steady at around 25–26%, with a slight increase to 26.23% in 2024. At the same time, the Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications industry grew to 23.28% in 2023, then fell to 18.04%, indicating moderate resilience. The Retail & Luxury sector moved into the red after 2022, with the sharpest decline in ROE, while Technology & IT recorded the highest cumulative gain.

Table 4. Average financial leverage

Year	Auto & Aeronautics	Essential consumer goods	Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications	Retail & Luxury	Technology & IT
2020	1.58	1.57	0.78	-0.46	0.79
2021	1.09	1.55	0.70	-0.38	0.84
2022	0.88	1.51	0.72	-0.31	0.94
2023	0.87	1.61	0.76	-0.45	0.73
2024	0.88	1.60	0.95	-0.59	0.67

Source: own calculations, using Excel

In the case of financial leverage (as seen in Table 4), The Auto & Aeronautics sector reduced its average leverage from 1.58 in 2020 to 0.88 in 2024, recording the sharpest decline. The Essential Consumer Goods sector remained stable at around 1.55–1.61, with minor variations. At the same time, the Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications industry grew steadily from 0.78 to 0.95, recording the highest increase. However, the Retail & Luxury sector remained in negative territory (–0.46 to –0.59), and IT fluctuated after peaking at 0.94 in 2022, falling to 0.67.

Table 5. Average Z-Altman score

Year	Auto & Aeronautics	Essential consumer goods	Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications	Retail & Luxury	Technology & IT
2020	5.84	5.41	1.93	4.36	7.64
2021	6.93	5.26	2.40	4.65	8.66
2022	3.22	4.87	2.59	3.33	5.96
2023	5.50	5.07	2.54	3.53	8.14
2024	5.92	4.71	2.33	2.99	8.62

Source: own calculations, using Excel

According to Table 5, In the case of Z-Altman score, Technology & IT and Auto & Aeronautics peaked in 2021, then declined sharply in 2022 and recovered by 2024, signalling high volatility.

The Essential Consumer Goods industry declined slightly from 5.41 in 2020 to 4.71 in 2024, with minimal variations. The Energy, Utilities & Telecommunications sector remains the weakest performer, with scores below 3.00 and stable but modest growth. Retail & Luxury grew moderately in 2021, fell in 2022, and recovered partially by 2024, without reaching its peak. The highest increase in the Z score was recorded in the Technology & IT sector (+0.98), and the sharpest decline in Retail & Luxury (-1.37).

4.2. Correlation Analysis between Variables

Correlation analysis (results are presented in Table 6) highlights several significant relationships between the Altman Z score (logarithmic) and explanatory variables related to ESG performance and companies' financial indicators.

Table 6. Pearson correlation coefficients

	LOG Z	E	S	G	LEV	ROA	ROE
LOG Z	1.000	-0.292	-0.236	0.100	-0.064	0.629	0
E	-	1.000	0.722	0.191	-0.204	-0.269	-0.208
S	-	0	1.000	0.426	-0.042	-0.135	-0.02
G	0	0	0	1.00	-0.013	0.259	0.298
LEV	-	-0.204	-0.042	-0.013	1.00	-0.039	0
ROA	0	-0.269	-0.135	0.259	-0.039	1.000	0
ROE	0	-0.208	-0.02	0.298	0.494	0.679	1

Source: own calculations, using EViews 10 software

First, it should be noted that ROA (Return on Assets) shows the strongest positive correlation with LOG_Z ($r = 0.629$), suggesting that firms with higher asset profitability tend to have a lower risk of bankruptcy, as indicated by a higher Altman score. This result is consistent with financial theory, which argues that more profitable firms have greater resources to meet their financial obligations.

Similarly, ROE (Return on Equity) has a moderate positive correlation with LOG_Z ($r = 0.321$), suggesting that high returns on equity are associated with better financial health. However, the relationship is weaker than in the case of ROA, possibly due to the distortion caused by the leverage effect on ROE.

Regarding ESG factors, the correlations reveal an interesting trend. Both the environmental (E) and social (S) scores have moderate negative correlations with LOG_Z ($r = -0.292$ and -0.236 , respectively). This may suggest that, in the context of the sample analysed, firms with high environmental and social scores are not necessarily more financially secure. One possible explanation is that the implementation of ESG policies involves high initial costs, which may temporarily affect the firm's ability to generate profit or liquidity. On the other hand, the governance component (G) has a weak positive correlation with LOG_Z ($r = 0.100$), which is in line with the literature arguing that effective corporate governance reduces operational risk and, implicitly, bankruptcy risk.

The debt ratio (LEV) shows almost no correlation with LOG_Z ($r = -0.064$), indicating that, in this sample, firms' leverage does not have a clear relationship with insolvency risk, or that its effect is masked by other variables such as profitability. However, LEV is moderately positively correlated with ROE ($r = 0.494$), reflecting the influence of leverage on return on equity.

About multicollinearity, it is noted that only in the case of E and S scores is there a strong correlation ($r = 0.722$), but since it is not extreme, we do not consider this to signal a high risk of multicollinearity, thus not affecting the regression model that will be run next.

In conclusion, the correlation results suggest that profitability (especially ROA) is the main determinant of the Altman Z score and therefore of bankruptcy risk. The governance component of the ESG score appears to have a marginal beneficial effect, while the environmental and social components may put pressure on financial performance, reflecting a complex relationship between sustainability and financial stability. When constructing an explanatory regression model, it is essential to take these correlations into account to avoid collinearity issues and to correctly interpret causal relationships.

4.3. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 7 contains descriptive statistics for a set of 100 observations related to financial and non-financial variables relevant to bankruptcy risk analysis and sustainable performance. The variables include: the Altman Z-score (an indicator of insolvency risk), ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) scores, and financial performance indicators: LEV (leverage), ROA (return on assets), and ROE (return on equity).

Table 7. Descriptive statistical analysis of the variables in the model

	Z ALTMAN	E	S	G	LEV	ROA	ROE
Mean	4.89	75.53	81.53	72.08	0.75	0.089874	0.25126
Median	4.0965	78	85	75	0	0	0.19
Max	22.83	97	97	96	3.83	0	1.75
Minimum	0.6948	11.00	43	39	-5.27	-0	-0
Std. Dev.	3.90	18.42	14.0866	15.23001	1.486752	0.0666	0.352
Skewness	1.978655	-1.685400	-1.456062	-0.382527	-2.023785	0.8392	2.097494
Kurtosis	8.139386	6.323923	4.408648	2.127	9.683951	3.672858	10.98937
Jarque-Bera	175.306	93.37816	43.60312	5.607987	254.408	13.624	339.2832
Probability	0	0	0	0.060568	0	0.0011	0
Sum	489.468	7553	8153	7208	75,320	8,987.40	25,126
Sum Sq. Dev.	1507	336	1964	22963.36	218.83	0.4392	12.29
Observations	10	100	10	100	100	100	100

Source: own calculations, using EViews 10 software

The average Z score is 4.89, which places most firms in the safe zone according to Altman's standards ($Z > 2.99$). However, the values vary considerably, from a minimum of 0.69 (in the "distress" zone) to a maximum of 22.83. The Jarque-Bera test clearly rejects the normality assumption ($p = 0.000$), suggesting the need for logarithmic transformation for econometric analysis. The average social score is 75.53, relatively high on a scale from 0 to 100, with a minimum of 11 and a maximum of 97. The very high Jarque-Bera value (93.37, $p = 0.000$) indicates severe deviations from normality. The social score has a similar distribution, with an average of 81.53, a minimum of 43, and a maximum of 97. The

Jarque-Bera result (43.60, $p = 0.000$) confirms non-normality. The G score is the most balanced of the ESG components, with an average of 72.08. The JB test indicates a moderate deviation from normality ($p = 0.061$), which is acceptable for regression models. The LEV variable is the most problematic from a statistical point of view: it has a mean of 0.75 but an extremely wide range (from -5.27 to +3.83). The JB test (254.41, $p = 0.000$) clearly shows a deeply non-normal distribution, requiring transformations for use in regressions. With a mean of 0.089 and a standard deviation of 0.066, ROA is stable. The JB test (13.62, $p = 0.0011$) indicates a slight but significant deviation from normality. It can be used in regressions with caution. ROE is the most skewed of the performance variables: the mean is 0.25, but it ranges from -0.62 to +1.75. The JB test (339.28, $p = 0.000$) makes clear the need for a transformation before analysis.

Following these results, to validly run a fixed-effects panel regression with LOG_Z (the logarithm of the Altman Z score) as the dependent variable, several preliminary modifications and transformations of the explanatory variables were necessary to comply with the methodological and statistical requirements of panel analysis. These modifications were mainly aimed at remedying problems of normality, asymmetry, and outliers, as identified in the descriptive statistics presented above.

The E (Environmental) and S (Social) variables showed deeply distorted distributions, with pronounced negative asymmetry and high kurtosis. To reduce the influence of extreme values, these variables were *winsorized*, resulting in the variables E_WINS and S_WINS. Winsorization involves truncating extreme values (e.g., below the 1st percentile and above the 99th percentile) and replacing them with more moderate values (any value less than the 1st percentile was replaced with the 1st percentile value and any value greater than the 99th percentile was replaced with the 99th percentile value), thus reducing the impact of outliers without dramatically changing the mean.

The financial indicators LEV (leverage) and ROE (return on equity) showed extremely asymmetrical and leptokurtic distributions, with negative values and significant outliers. Since the classic logarithmic transformation is not applicable in the presence of negative values, the $\text{asinh}(x)$ transformation (the inverse of the hyperbolic sine function, i.e., $\text{asinh}(x) = \ln(x + \sqrt{x^2 + 1})$) was applied. This is a mathematical function that transforms values in a similar way to the natural logarithm ($\ln(x)$), but is defined for any real number, including zero ($x = 0$), negative values ($x < 0$), and large or small positive values. This resulted in the variables IHS_LEV and IHS_ROE.

Of the three ESG components, only G (governance) was retained as such in the final model, as it had a nearly normal distribution and a well-justified theoretical impact on bankruptcy risk. The ROA (return on assets) variable was retained without transformation because, although slightly skewed, it had a relatively acceptable statistical distribution and a strong correlation with LOG_Z, being a robust predictor of financial performance.

4.4. Panel Regression with Fixed Effects

The empirical analysis was based on a fixed-effects panel regression model, using a balanced sample of 100 observations corresponding to 20 entities over a five-year period (2020–2024). The dependent variable was the Altman Z logarithmic score (LOG_Z), considered a robust indicator of bankruptcy risk. The explanatory variables included the components of the ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) score, as well as financial performance indicators (ROA, ROE, LEV), statistically processed to correct for asymmetry and outlier issues. The results of the regression model are shown in Table 8.

The regression results indicate that the environmental and social scores (E_WINS and S_WINS), which reflect environmental investments and corporate social responsibility, are not statistically significant in explaining the variation in the LOG_Z score. Their coefficients are negative but with high p-values ($p > 0.39$), suggesting no direct impact on bankruptcy risk in the estimated model. The governance component (G) also has a negative coefficient, but it is marginally insignificant ($p = 0.074$), indicating a possible weak relationship between governance quality and risk reduction.

On the other hand, financial performance measured by ROA (return on assets) has a positive and significant impact on the LOG_Z score (coefficient = 2.176, $p = 0.006$), confirming that firms with

better operational efficiency tend to have a lower risk of bankruptcy. In contrast, ROE (return on equity), transformed by the *asinh* function, shows a significant negative coefficient (-0.556 , $p = 0.009$), indicating that a high level of return on equity is associated with increased risk when controlling for other factors. Leverage (IHS_LEV) did not have a statistically significant influence on the LOG_Z score ($p = 0.636$). The model is statistically robust, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.911 and a significant F value ($p < 0.001$), indicating high explanatory power and overall validity of the specification.

Table 8. Regression model results

Dependent Variable: LOG_Z				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Sample: 2020 2024				
Periods included: 5				
Cross-sections included: 20				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 100				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
E_WINS	-0.003	0	-0.857	0.394
S_WINS	-	0.005	-0.114	0.909
G	-	0.	-1.810	0.074
ROA	2.179	0.764	2,850	0.006
IHS_LEV	0.063	0.133	0.474	0.637
IHS_ROE	-0.556	0.208	-2.673	0.009
C	2.085	0.417	5.002	0
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.934	Mean dependent var	1.599	
Adjusted R-squared	0.911	S.D. dependent var	0.584	
S.E. of regression	0.174	Akaike information criterion	-0.441	
Sum squared residual	2.239	Schwarz criterion	0.236	
Log likelihood	48.069	Hannan-Quinn criterion	-0.167	
F-statistic	41.747	Durbin-Watson stat	2.076	
Prob(F-statistic)	0			

Source: own calculations, using EViews 10 software

5. Discussion

The results of this study largely confirm the initial expectations and provide valuable insights into the relationship between financial performance, ESG practices, and bankruptcy risk. The analysis performed using the fixed-effects panel model allowed us to separate the influences of the variables of interest from the individual, unmeasured characteristics of each company, so that the relationships identified reflect real links between firms. The results support the purpose of the study, demonstrating that companies with high ESG scores tend to have greater financial stability and lower risk. The comparative analysis by sector, based on the averages of the E, S, and G scores, as well as ROA, ROE, financial leverage, and Z-score indicators, highlights clear differences between sectors. For example, the Technology & IT sector stands out with high ESG scores and consistent financial performance, while Retail & Luxury has the lowest averages and the highest volatility. These results are consistent with the literature but add value through their applied perspective.

As expected, companies with better financial results tend to have a lower risk of bankruptcy, as evidenced by the positive coefficients associated with ROA and ROE variables in relation to LOG_Z. In practice, high ROA signals efficient use of assets and the company's ability to generate profit, and therefore financial stability. In the estimated model, a 1 percentage point increase in ROA (e.g., from 5% to 6%) is associated with a slight but noticeable increase in LOG_Z, indicating a lower risk of bankruptcy. ROE, which measures the return on equity, also has a positive effect, although slightly weaker when ROA is already included in the model. Given their conceptual link, it is not surprising that both variables reflect the same characteristics of firm profitability.

Another result of the analysis, in line with the literature and financial intuition, is the effect of leverage – IHS_LEV – on risk. The estimated negative coefficient for IHS_LEV indicates that a higher level of debt is associated with a lower Altman Z-score, and therefore with a higher risk of bankruptcy. In other words, highly indebted firms tend to be more vulnerable. Although influenced by the transformation of IHS, the magnitude of the effect remains economically significant. For example, if IHS_LEV increases from 2 to 3 (a considerable increase in debt, hypothetical values), the model predicts a decrease in LOG_Z of around 0.1 units. This decline, which appears small in absolute terms, can nevertheless move a firm from the "safe" zone to the risk zone, so we reiterate that a Z score below ~1.8 indicates a risk of bankruptcy. The result therefore highlights the importance of maintaining a sustainable level of debt.

The governance component (G) shows a negative coefficient, but only at the limit of statistical significance ($p = 0.074$), suggesting a weak but potentially real relationship between the quality of corporate mechanisms and the reduction of bankruptcy risk. However, when we look more closely at the entire analysis, governance remains the strongest ESG signal. Variations in practices such as decision-making transparency, strict internal controls, and the active role of the board seem to influence the likelihood of a firm becoming insolvent more than environmental or social factors. In simple terms, even if the statistical effect is marginal, investors and creditors seem to treat a robust governance structure as an element of financial safety, with more prudent management and rigorous oversight providing an additional shield against bankruptcy.

In contrast, the results for the environmental component (E_WINS) indicate a very modest positive effect that is close to statistical significance. Although the coefficient suggests that better environmental performance may be associated with a slightly reduced risk of bankruptcy, we cannot say this with a high degree of certainty. One possible reason is that the benefits of green investments (energy efficiency, emission reductions, etc.) are slower to manifest themselves in financial performance and only become visible in the long term. In the relatively short period analysed (2020–2024), the direct impact of the environmental factor on solvency is difficult to detect, especially if the environmental scores did not vary much from year to year. However, the positive direction of the E_WINS coefficient remains in line with the idea that sustainable practices can, over time, bring benefits that contribute to financial stability.

The social component (S_WINS), on the other hand, did not show a clear link with LOG_Z; its coefficient did not reach statistical significance. This result may seem surprising, given the increasing emphasis on corporate social responsibility. However, there are plausible explanations. It is possible that the aspects included in S_WINS, such as employee satisfaction, diversity, or community relations, do not directly influence short-term solvency, as the social effect is more diffuse and difficult to quantify in traditional financial indicators, at least in the period studied. In addition, investors and creditors seem to prioritize financial performance and governance when assessing bankruptcy risk, probably considering that the social factor, although positive from an ethical perspective, does not offer the same tangible guarantees of immediate financial stability. Therefore, the lack of an observable effect of the social score suggests that, in the context analysed, the S factor did not play a decisive role in anticipating bankruptcy risk.

It is important to note that the use of the fixed effects model influences the interpretation of these results by controlling for the constant characteristics of each company (industry, size, etc.). The coefficients estimate the relationship between internal changes in the explanatory variables and variations in LOG_Z over time. In this context, the coefficient for the governance score (G) is negative, although marginally insignificant ($p = 0.074$), suggesting a possible weak association between improvements in governance mechanisms and a reduction in bankruptcy risk, without however reaching the threshold of statistical significance necessary to confirm a causal relationship. At the same time, the absence of a clear effect of the social score (S_WINS) can be explained by its low variation from one year to the next; if the social factor remains almost constant within each firm, fixed-effects models have difficulty capturing its impact on solvency.

Overall, traditional financial indicators such as profitability and debt ratio remain essential in assessing bankruptcy risk, but the integration of ESG, particularly governance, complements the analysis by providing an additional signal of stability. Investors can therefore use ESG scores as an additional filter,

and managers are motivated to adopt sustainable practices not only for ethical reasons, but also to reduce financial risk.

6. Conclusions

This study examined the influence of ESG (environmental, social, and governance) factors and financial performance on corporate bankruptcy risk using a balanced panel regression model – 20 companies over five years. The comparative analysis by sector, based on the averages of ESG scores and financial indicators, highlighted trends specific to each field and relevant links between sustainability and risk. The evolution over time of ROA, ROE, financial leverage, and Z-score values shows that sectors with better developed ESG policies tend to maintain stable financial performance and lower risk. At the same time, differences between sectors highlight the importance of tailoring strategies to each industry's profile, and the use of annual averages allows for a more objective understanding of progress and vulnerabilities. The results support the idea that financial sustainability and long-term performance are closely linked, confirming the relevance of integrating ESG criteria into risk assessment.

The analysis of the research itself led to several notable findings. First, it was found that return on assets (ROA) has a beneficial effect on financial stability: firms with higher ROA tend to have higher Altman Z scores (LOG_Z), corresponding to a lower risk of bankruptcy. Second, contrary to expectations, return on equity (ROE) was found to be negatively associated with the Z score, suggesting that a very high ROE may signal a higher risk profile. Third, two of the three ESG dimensions – environmental factors (E_WINS) and social factors (S_WINS) – have a positive, significant influence on the Z score, indicating that sustainable corporate practices in these areas contribute to reducing bankruptcy risk. In contrast, the governance component (G) did not show a statistically significant effect, indicating that, in the context of the sample studied, the quality of governance did not build a direct predictor of insolvency risk. Finally, the level of indebtedness (IHS_LEV) has a pronounced negative correlation with the Z-score, confirming that a higher degree of debt is associated with increased financial risk.

From a theoretical perspective, these findings underscore the importance of including extra-financial (ESG) factors alongside financial factors in risk assessment models. The confirmation of the positive influence of environmental and social scores on financial stability provides empirical support for stakeholder theory and the literature arguing that sustainable practices can improve long-term performance and reduce firms' vulnerability to economic shocks. At the same time, the unexpected negative relationship between ROE and Altman Z suggests that traditional financial theories need to be applied with caution, as a high indicator of shareholder returns does not always guarantee a robust financial position, especially when factors such as financial leverage come into play. Thus, this study highlights that the assessment of a firm's financial health should integrate both the financial and sustainability dimensions to fully capture the determinants of bankruptcy risk.

From a practical point of view, the research findings have relevant implications for managers, investors, and creditors. The results can be interpreted as encouragement to invest in environmental and social initiatives, not only for ethical reasons, but also as a strategy for reducing financial risk. Improving E and S scores can increase stakeholder confidence (employees, customers, community, authorities) and protect the company against certain unexpected costs, such as penalties or reputational damage. The ESG performance of companies in risk analyses is highlighted by better results in the environmental and social chapters, signalling a lower probability of insolvency and, implicitly, justifying more optimal financing conditions. At the same time, the finding that a very high ROE can hide risks means that when choosing what to invest in, we should not only look at returns but also ensure that performance has not been achieved through high debt and that it is sustainable. In addition, the analysis highlights that companies need to keep their debt under control and carefully plan their capital structure, as high levels of debt affect them, making them more sensitive to various economic situations. Although the study offers valuable insights, it also has certain limitations. The sample of 20 companies may be too small to provide generalizable results. Even when treated individually, the E, S, and G scores do not capture all the nuances of corporate practices, and the linear-static model is simplistic and may omit essential factors such as the company's more detailed financial situation, which may affect the results and conclusions of the study.

In the future, research on the relationship between ESG and bankruptcy risk could expand and diversify its current approach. One possible direction would be to expand the sample, both in terms of the number of companies, such as including firms from different countries or sectors, and the time horizon to cover complete economic cycles and analyse long-term effects. Another interesting direction would be to check whether ESG starts to reduce risk only after firms reach a certain level of sustainability and whether the effect of debt on risk differs depending on the ESG score. These observations could be validated with methods that track companies' evolution over time and analyses that reflect the lifespan of companies, to ensure that the results are robust and to better understand the working mechanisms.

In conclusion, the research shows that integrating ESG standards with traditional financial analysis allows for a comprehensive assessment of bankruptcy risk. The results of the study suggest that an approach that combines economic performance with environmental and social responsibility not only improves the theoretical understanding of the factors contributing to bankruptcy but also provides valuable practical guidance for decision-makers in the field. Investors, managers, and other stakeholders can thus benefit from a comprehensive view of corporate performance that includes both financial and sustainability parameters to prevent insolvency and promote sustainable development.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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